

Inoculation results indicate that adding a single gene (*Xa21*) is sufficient to confer resistance to all seven Philippine races of *Xoo* and 20 isolates from China, Colombia, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Nepal, and Thailand. Resistance to *Xoo* strains of Philippine races 1 through 6 cosegregated with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) profile of the *Xa21* transgene in a 3:1 ratio. Southern blot analysis confirmed the PCR results, indicating that a single member of the *Xa21* multigene family can confer resistance to diverse strains isolated from seven countries.

The *Xa21* gene family contains eight members, all located at the *Xa21* locus. Each member contains an LRR motif.

Differences in the LRR domain of the family may play a role in the specificity of pathogen recognition. To test this idea, we generated transgenic plants carrying subclones from other members of the *Xa21* gene family. The resistance of these lines to the six *Xoo* races has been determined. Preliminary screening showed that at least one copy (copy D) confers partial resistance to races 1 and 6 in transgenic plants.

To analyze the expression of the *Xa21* gene family, we made a cDNA library from the resistant line infected with *Xoo*. We identified 17 cDNAs hybridizing with LRR or/and kinase domains. Sequencing results indicate that at least four copies of the gene family are expressed.

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A bacterial blight-resistant, wide-compatible indica line

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In China, scientists started to develop innovative elite lines with genes for resistance to bacterial blight (BB) *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) in the early 1980s. Scientists are now using wide compatibility as an approach to develop indica/japonica hybrid rice through pyramiding genes for wide compatibility, disease resistance, and agronomically important characters.

We determined resistance to BB by evaluating lesion length 20 d after inoculation (9×10^8 cells ml⁻¹ concentration) using the clipping method at booting stage. We used 10 *Xoo* isolates (provided by the Plant Protection Department, Nanjing Agricultural University) of major pathotypes I through VII from different provinces in China: OS14 (I) (Liaoning),

KS-6-6 (II) (Jiangsu), HB84-17 (II) (Heibe), OS105 (II) (Guangdong), FJ856 (III) (Fujian), ZHE173 (IV) (Zhejiang), AH023 (IV) (Anfei), GD1358 (V) (Guangdong), GX325 (V) (Guangxi), and JS49-6 (VII) (Hunan).

We evaluated wide compatibility using spikelet fertility from testcrosses to both typical indica and japonica cultivars. Mean fertility of unbagged F₁ plants was assessed at maturity. Spikelet fertility of up to 70% was normal and compatible.

85-21416 is a promising indica line developed from a 1978 cross between Taichung Native 1, a susceptible and noncompatible indica cultivar from Taiwan, China, and DZ78, a highly resistant, tall indica from Bangladesh. 85-21416 has strong resistance to BB and is extremely compatible in intersubspecific crosses. We grew F₃ lines of this cross combination in early spring of 1980. We then selected individuals each year through artificial inoculation evaluation. By 1985, 85-21416 along with other advanced lines (F₇₋₈) were selected for stable resistance and other

characters. 85-21416 was used in 1988 as a resistance donor in intersubspecific genetic studies.

The shorter lesion lengths of 85-21416 confirmed its stable BB resistance (Table 1). A recessive gene allelic to *xa5* (data not shown) controls the resistance. 85-21416 may have inherited the resistance

Table 2. F₁ spikelet fertilities of 85-21416 crossed with various tester varieties.^a

Cross combination ^b	Mean	Plants (no.)
Balilla/85-21416	87.3 ± 3.58	15
Aikihikari/85-21416	91.7 ± 3.20	14
85-21416/IR36	87.9 ± 5.04	6
02428/85-21416	79.4 ± 5.28	12
Ketan Nangka/ 85-21416	62.5 ± 1.41	18
85-21416/CPSL017	68.4 ± 1.73	18
85-21416 (I)	80.6 ± 5.31	14
Balilla (J)	67.9 ± 4.86	12
Aikihikari (J)	89.3 ± 3.51	10
02428 (J)	71.4 ± 7.06	10
IR36 (I)	92.9 ± 1.05	15
CPSL017 (I)	82.6 ± 3.00	10

^aData were collected in 1992, except those for 85-21416/IR36 and IR36, which were collected in Sep 1995. ^bI = indica, J = japonica.

Table 1. Reactions of 85-21416 to bacterial blight isolates compared with Nanjing 11, DV85, and IRBB7.

Line/variety	Gene	Isolates										Evaluation criterion	Year
		OS14	HB84-17	KS-6-6	OS105	FJ856	ZHE173	AH023	GD1358	GX325	JS94-6		
85-21416	<i>xa5(t)</i>	1.7	1.4	1.8	0.8	1.1	1.1	1.5	3.9	1.6	0.6	Lesion length (cm)	1994
DV85	<i>xa5, Xa7</i>	1.2	1.1	1.2	1.5	1.1	1.3	1.3	0.7	1.6	0.9	Lesion length (cm)	1994
IRBB117	<i>Xa7</i>	-	3.0	-	-	-	3.0	-	5.0	-	3.0	Leaf area necrotized (%)	1995
Nanjing 11	None	19.8	26.1	25.8	20.6	13.1	19.8	23.7	9.7	25.6	10.2	Lesion length (cm)	1994

gene from DZ78, which carries *xa5* and *xa7*.

F₁ hybrids derived from crosses between 85-21416 and 16 japonica cultivars in 1989 were fertile, with 84.2 ± 2.8% average spikelet fertility. 85-21416 carries a

compatibility gene that appears allelic to *S-5ⁿ*. Fairly fertile hybrids were obtained from crosses between 85-21416 and cultivars known to have the wide-compatibility gene *S-5ⁿ* (Ketan Nangka, CPSL017, and 02428) (Table 2). The

compatibility gene carried by 85-21416 could have come from indica DZ78, which produced a compatible intersubspecific hybrid when crossed with japonica tester cultivar Akihikari (69.1 ± 1.1% spikelet fertility in 1992). ■

RFLP mapping of blast resistance gene *Pi-k^m* in rice

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Blast resistance gene *Pi-k* is located on chromosome 11 (Goto et al 1981) and has multiple alleles *Pi-k^h*, *Pi-k^m*, and *Pi-k^p* (Kiyosawa 1978). Although restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) linkage analysis indicated that *Pi-k* is located on chromosome 11, no RFLP marker closely linked to *Pi-k* was found at that time. For fine-mapping of *Pi-k* loci, we conducted RFLP analysis of *Pi-k^m* and

RFLP markers using F₃ lines from the cross between Tohoku IL4 (japonica near-isogenic line with *Pi-k^m* introgressed from Tsuyuake) and CO 39 (susceptible indica variety).

Each F₃ line was inoculated with Japanese blast race 003 at 3-4 leaf stage using the spray method. The F₃ lines were classified either as resistant (or segregating) lines or susceptible lines 30 d after inoculation.

DNA was extracted from the leaves of each F₃ line using the cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide method. Total DNA was digested with restriction enzymes (*Eco*RI, *Hind*III, and *Dra*I) and blotted onto a positively charged nylon membrane filter using capillary transfer after electrophoresis. RFLP landmarks on chromosome 11 and

cDNA clone R1506 (provided by NIAR/STAFF) were used. Linkage analyses of *Pi-k^m* and the RFLP markers are shown in the table. Recombination values calculated using the maximum likelihood method were converted into genetic map distances (cM) using the Kosambi function. All RFLP markers used in this study were linked to *Pi-k^m*, notably L190, which was closely linked to *Pi-k^m* at about 1.5 cM.

Pi-k^m is located on chromosome 11 in the RFLP linkage map between L190 and R1506 (see figure). Because L190 is located on the terminal region of chromosome 11 (Nagamura et al 1993), results of our study correspond to those of a classical linkage map. For further fine-mapping of the *Pi-k^m* loci, we will subject more F₃ lines to RFLP analysis. ■

Linkage analysis among *Pi-k^m* and RFLP markers.

Gene pair		Segregation mode in F ₃										Genetic map distance (cM)
A	B	AABB	AABb	AAbb	AaBB	AaBb	Aabb	aaBB	aaBb	aabb		
<i>Pi-k^m</i>	L190	36	61	1				0	1	37	1.5 ± 1.2	
	R1506	29	47	3				0	2	32	4.3 ± 1.0	
	G181	28	62	5				0	7	34	8.4 ± 1.9	
	G1465	31	80	12				1	12	32	15.8 ± 2.4	
L190	R1506	26	5	1	1	31	2	0	1	27	6.0 ± 2.6	
	G181	26	3	1	0	42	5	0	6	29	7.4 ± 1.8	
	G1465	20	13	3	6	48	8	1	10	27	19.1 ± 3.0	
R1506	G181	23	3	0	3	37	3	0	6	27	7.7 ± 1.8	
	G1465	18	10	1	8	33	8	0	9	26	18.5 ± 1.9	
G181	G1465	19	8	1	6	54	9	0	8	31	13.3 ± 2.8	

Linkage map of *Pi-k^m* and RFLP markers on chromosome 11.

Indica/japonica doubled haploid population as a model for mapping rice yellow mottle virus and blast resistance genes

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Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) is the most damaging rice pest in irrigated fields of West Africa. Blast is a widespread disease causing severe yield losses. To map several resistance genes, we used two doubled haploid (DH) populations derived from the F₁ hybrids IR64/Azucena and IRAT 177/Apuraj and segregating for many agronomic traits. This analysis relied on core restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) maps developed at IRRI for the IR64/Azucena population (Huang et al 1994) and at Cornell University for the IRAT 177/Apuraj population (Yu et al 1991).

RYMV scoring. The resistance analysis involved 74 IR64/Azucena DH lines and 48 IRAT 177/Apuraj DH lines. Nineteen-day-old rice plants were mechanically inoculated with a RYMV isolate collected from Mali. Two weeks after inoculation, newly emerged leaves were harvested for assessment of virus concentration by serological methods involving ACP- or DAS-enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays.

Blast scoring. An initial survey involving the parents and 20 IR64/Azucena DH lines allowed us to select six diverse strains of *Magnaporthe grisea* apparently inter-